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**THE EFFECT OF LEADERSHIP AND WORK DISCIPLINE
 ON PERFORMANCE WITH MOTIVATION AS A VARIABLE INTERVENING
 (CASE STUDY: DPRD SECRETARIAT REGENCY LABUHAN BATU)**

**ВПЛИВ ЛІДЕРСТВА ТА ТРУДОВОЇ ДИСЦИПЛІНИ
 НА РЕЗУЛЬТАТИВНІСТЬ ІЗ МОТИВАЦІЄЮ ЯК ЗМІННОЮ
 (ПРИКЛАД: СЕКРЕТАРІАТ DPRD REGENCY LABUHAN BATU)**

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Chairully, Syaifuddin, Cut Fitri Rostina, Rosita. Вплив лідерства та трудової дисципліни на результативність із мотивацією як змінною (приклад: Секретаріат DPRD Regency Labuhan Batu). Оглядова стаття.

Людські ресурси є найважливішим активом у досягненні цілей організації, оскільки людські ресурси відіграють важливу роль у кожній організаційній діяльності. Без ролі людських ресурсів діяльність всередині організації не може відбуватися належним чином. Це показує, що людські ресурси є основним ключем, який необхідно враховувати. Це дослідження має на меті визначити, чи впливають лідерство та трудова дисципліна на продуктивність співробітників через мотивацію як проміжну змінну в Секретаріаті DPRD Регентства Лабуханбату. Дослідження проводилося на 53 співробітниках за методикою насиченої вибірки. Використана техніка збору даних: первинні дані у формі анкет та вторинні дані, отримані шляхом вивчення документації. Техніка аналізу даних використовувала кількісні дані, які були оброблені за допомогою програми SPSS версії 25, а саме t-тест, тест Собея та аналіз шляхів.

Ключові слова: лідерство, трудова дисципліна, мотивація, продуктивність

Chairully, Syaifuddin, Cut Fitri Rostina, Rosita. The Effect of Leadership and Work Discipline on Performance With Motivation as a Variable Intervening (Case Study: DPRD Secretariat Regency Labuhan Batu). Review article.

Human resources are the most important asset in achieving the goals of an organization, because human resources have an important role in every organizational activity. Without the role of human resources, activities within the organization cannot run properly. This shows that human resources are the main key that must be considered. This study aims to determine whether leadership and work discipline affect employee performance through motivation as an intervening variable at the DPRD Secretariat of Labuhanbatu Regency. The study was conducted on 53 employees using a saturated sampling technique. The data collection technique used was primary data in the form of questionnaires and secondary data obtained through documentation studies. The data analysis technique used quantitative data which was processed using the SPSS version 25 program, namely the t test, Sobel test and path analysis.

Keywords: leadership, work discipline, motivation, performance

Human resources are an asset paramount in achieving a goal organization, because of human resources has an important role in every activity organization. Without the role of resources human beings, activities within the organization cannot goes well. It shows that human resources is the key point to pay attention to .Human resource issues are still in the spotlight and foundation for the company to survive in the era globalization. Human resources have a major role in every organizational activity. Even though it's supported with facilities and infrastructure as well as resources redundant, but without the support of human resources reliable, organizational activities will not be resolved well. This indicates that the resource Humans are the main key that must be considered with all their needs. Increasing organization developing will always think of effective work efficient and easy to control and assess implementation so that it is easy to determine employee performance .The Main Duties of the Secretariat of the DPRD Labuhanbatu Regency carry out secretarial and financial administration, support carrying out the duties and functions of the DPRD, as well as providing and coordinating the experts needed by the DPRD in providing their rights and functions as needed. In carrying out its duties, the DPRD Secretariat has the following functions:

1. Organizing DPRD secretariat administration;

2. Implementation of DPRD financial administration;
3. Facilitating the holding of DPRD meetings;
4. Provision and coordination of experts needed by DPRD;
5. Implementation of other tasks given by the Regent in accordance with his duties and functions.

The main part

Improving employee performance at the Labuhanbatu Regency DPRD Secretariat requires several things such as leadership and work discipline as well as high motivation, good leadership and work discipline will support employees to be able to improve their performance. Based on the results of the observations of researchers on employees of the Secretariat of the DPRD Labuhanbatu Regency still found some unfinished work on time, employees arrive late, and permission does not come to work for reasons that are not too important, this results in decreased employee performance and indicates low employee motivation at work. From the description

above, it can be seen that there is problems between phenomena and expectations as well theoretical support related to style leadership, motivation, work discipline and performance, so the writer is interested in doing this research.

METHODS. The research was conducted at the DPRD Secretariat office in Labuhanbatu Regency. Meanwhile, the research was conducted from October 2022 to January 2023.

This research is included in the associative research approach quantitative. This study examines the relationship between the variables Leadership (X_1) and Work Discipline (X_2) to the Performance variable (Y) with Motivation (Z) as the intervening variable. In this study the approach used is approach quantitative because the data used to analyze the influence between variables expressed by numbers or a numerical scale (Kuncoro, 2011, in Wulandari, 2015).

RESULT. 1 Testing the Classical Assumptions of Sub Model I. Multicollinearity Test Table for Sub Model I.

Table 1. Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	VIF
1	(Constant)	49.765	6.682			
	Leadership	0.154	0.199	0.163	0.952	1.050
	Work Discipline	0.134	0.107	0.144	0.952	1.050

a. Dependent Variable: Motivation

Source: authors' own elaboration

The results of the multicollinearity test show that the VIF and tolerance values are as follows: The leadership variable (X_1) has a VIF value of 1.050 and a tolerance of 0.952. The work discipline variable (X_2) has a VIF value of 1.050 and a tolerance of 0.952. From these provisions that if the VIF value < 10 and tolerance > 0.10 then there are no symptoms of multicollinearity and the values obtained from the calculations are in accordance with the provisions of

VIF and tolerance values, it can be concluded that the independent variables do not occur multicollinearity so that the model has meets the classical assumption requirements in regression analysis.

2. Sub Model Hypothesis Test I.

The hypothesis states that Leadership (X_1), Work Discipline (X_2), has a positive and significant effect on Motivation (Z). The following table 4.12 results of the calculation of the t-test for each variable (table 2).

Table 2. Test Results for Sub Model I. Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	B		
1	(Constant)	49.765	6.682		7.448	0.000
	Leadership	0.154	0.199	0.163	1.546	0.007
	Work Discipline	0.134	0.107	0.144	1.250	0.015

a. Dependent Variable: Motivation

Source: authors' own elaboration

In the table, the t statistical test is obtained as follows:

1) Leadership variable (X_1) with a probability level of 0.007. Thus it can be concluded that $P = 0.007 < \alpha = 0.05$, accept the hypothesis that leadership has a significant effect on motivational variables.

2) Work Discipline Variable (X_2) with a probability level of 0.015. Thus it can be concluded that $P = 0.015 < \alpha = 0.05$, so accept the hypothesis that the work discipline variable has a significant effect on the motivation variable.

Thus the path analysis equation can be arranged as follows:

$$Z = 0.163 X_1 + 0.144 X_2$$

The analysis equation model means:

1) Leadership Variable (X_1) = 0.163 Leadership variables that are positive means that they have a unidirectional influence, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the leadership variable will increase the value of the motivational variable by 0.163 per one unit score.

2) Work Discipline Variable (X_2) = 0.144. The work discipline variable that has a positive sign means that it has a unidirectional effect, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit score for the work discipline variable will increase the value of the motivation variable by 0.144 per one unit score.

3. Path Analysis of Sub Model I.

Referring to the regression output of Sub Model I, it can be seen that the significance value of the two variables, namely Leadership (X_1) = 0.007 and Work Discipline (X_2) = 0.015. These results conclude that the regression of Sub Model I, namely the Leadership variable (X_1) has a significant effect on Competence (Z), and the Work Discipline variable (X_2) has a significant effect on Motivation (Z). The value of R^2 or R Square contained in the Model Summary table is 0.231. This indicates that the contribution or influence of the Leadership variable (X_1) and Work Discipline (X_2) on the Performance variable (Z) is 80%, while the remaining 20 % is the contribution of other variables not included in the study. Meanwhile, for value $\hat{\epsilon}$ 1 can be found by the formula $\hat{\epsilon} 1 = \sqrt{(1-0.231)} = 0.876$.

4. Sobel test.

Testing the mediation hypothesis can also be carried out with a procedure developed by Sobel and known as the Sobel test (Sobel test). The Sobel test is carried out by testing the strength of the indirect influence X to Y through Z, as follows:

$$Z = \frac{ab}{\sqrt{b^2 SE_a^2 + a^2 SE_b^2}}, \quad (1)$$

where a – regression coefficient of the independent variable on the mediating variable,

b – regression coefficient of the mediating variable on the dependent variable,

SE_a – standard error of estimation from the influence of the independent variable on the mediating variable,

SE_b – standard error of estimation of the effect of the mediating variable on the dependent variable.

Following are the results of the Sobel test with leadership variables on performance through motivation.

$$t = \frac{0.163 \times 0.022}{\sqrt{(0.022^2 \times 0.199^2) + (0.163^2 \times 0.104^2)}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.163 \times 0.022}{\sqrt{0.000019166884 + 0.000287370304}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.003586}{0.000306537188}$$

$$t = 11.698.$$

From the results of the calculation of the sobel test above, the t value is 11.698, so that the t value is $11.698 > t$ table 4.447. It can be concluded that the motivational variable is able to mediate the relationship between the influence of leadership on performance.

Following are the results of the Sobel test with work discipline variables on performance through motivation.

$$t = \frac{0.144 \times 0.022}{\sqrt{(0.022^2 \times 0.107^2) + (0.144^2 \times 0.104^2)}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.144 \times 0.022}{\sqrt{0.000005541316 + 0.000224280576}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.003168}{0.000229821892}$$

$$t = 13.784.$$

From the results of the calculation of the sobel test above, the t value is 13.784, so that the t value is $13.784 > t$ table 4.447. It can be concluded that the motivation variable is able to mediate the relationship between the influence of work discipline on performance.

Conclusions

1. Leadership has a positive and significant effect on motivation at the District DPRD Secretariat, Labuhanbatu. This means that this condition proves that leadership can increase employee motivation.

2. Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on motivation at the District DPRD Secretariat, Labuhanbatu. This means that this condition proves that work discipline can increase employee motivation.

3. Leadership has a positive and significant effect on performance at the District DPRD Secretariat, Labuhanbatu. This means that this condition proves that leadership can improve performance.

4. Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on performance at the District DPRD Secretariat, Labuhanbatu. This means that this condition proves that work discipline can improve employee performance.

5. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on performance at the District DPRD Secretariat, Labuhanbatu. This means that this condition proves that the higher the motivation of employees can improve performance.

6. The influence of leadership on the performance of employees of the DPRD Secretariat Kab. Labuhanbatu will be smaller if done through motivation. The direct effect of leadership on employee performance is greater than the indirect effect of leadership on performance. It can be

concluded that motivation is not able to mediate the influence of leadership on performance.

7. The effect of work discipline on the performance of employees of the DPRD Secretariat Kab. Labuhanbatu will be bigger if done through

motivation. The direct effect of work discipline on performance is greater than the indirect effect of work discipline on performance. It can be concluded that motivation is not able to mediate the effect of work discipline on performance.

Abstract

Human resources are the most important asset in achieving the goals of an organization, because human resources have an important role in every organizational activity. Without the role of human resources, activities within the organization cannot run properly. This shows that human resources are the main key that must be considered. This study aims to determine whether leadership and work discipline affect employee performance through motivation as an intervening variable at the DPRD Secretariat of Labuhanbatu Regency. The study was conducted on 53 employees using a saturated sampling technique. The data collection technique used was primary data in the form of questionnaires and secondary data obtained through documentation studies. The data analysis technique used quantitative data which was processed using the SPSS version 25 program, namely the t test, Sobel test and path analysis. The results obtained in this study show 1) there is a significant influence between leadership on motivation, 2) there is a significant effect between work discipline variables on motivation, 3) there is a significant influence between leadership variables on performance, 4) there is a significant influence between work discipline variables on performance, 5) there is a significant influence between motivational variables on performance, 6) motivational variables cannot influence leadership variables on performance, 7) motivational variables cannot affect work discipline variables on performance.

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